

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PROGRAMME BUDGETING SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Programme budgeting system is a system of budget execution planning, implementation and control that ensures the interdependence of the process of allocation of budgets of the budget system of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the results of the implementation of programs developed on the basis of strategic goals, taking into account the priorities of the policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the results of the use of budget funds.

Target indicator (Performance Indicators) is an indicator used to evaluate the qualitative and quantitative indicators that ultimately achieve the goals set in the development programs.

The final result indicator (Outcome) is an indicator that describes the main goal to be achieved and reflects the qualitative and quantitative change in the situation of the funding agencies in the relevant field of activity;

Direct (direct) result indicator (Output) is an indicator that describes the amount of work performed, services provided and goods purchased for each event.

A budget program is a set of sub-programs and/or activities aimed at accomplishing specific tasks financed from the budgets of the budget system and achieving the goals defined in the strategic development documents.

Sub-programme is a component of the budget program, a set of several activities on interrelated lines of activity aimed at achieving a specific result;

An activity is a part of a budget program or sub-program and includes one activity aimed at solving a work or service (a specific problem).

Adopted regulatory documents on the introduction of the program budgeting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

1. In accordance with the decision No. 506 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 24.08.2020 "On approval of the strategy for improving the public finance management system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2024" in order to implement a strategic approach to the tax-budget policy, the new "Result-oriented budgeting" of the formation of the annual budget (Program budgeting) system is set to be introduced.

2. According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4555 of 30.12.2019, the budgets of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Health, the Committee of Highways and the Ministry of Water Management for 2021 in accordance with the result-oriented budgeting system, determining the quality and quantity indicators of the expenses formation is defined.

Also, with this decision, it is established to establish a Department of Budget Expenditure Efficiency Assessment and Implementation of Programmatic Target Methods of Budget Planning, consisting of 5 state units, within the framework of the state units defined in the structure of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3. By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 30.12.2020 No. PQ-4938, the indicators of the effectiveness of budget expenditures of the Ministries of Health Care, Water Management, Public Education, Water Management and the Committee of Motorways were approved as a test.

4. By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-73 dated 30.12.2021, the target indicators of 40 ministerial departments were approved.

5. Decision PQ-422 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 25.12.2023 approved the target indicators of 37 ministerial offices.

6. On January 4, 2024, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4 on approving the procedure for the development, monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the budget programs of allocators of budget funds was approved.

7. According to the 46th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 on the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" No. PF-158, the introduction of the "Result-oriented budgeting" system is established.

Implementation of program budgeting system in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 2021:

The target indicators of the Ministries of Health, Public Education, Water Management and the Road Committee were approved as a trial:

- a total of 14.9 trillion soums budget or 9.2% of state budget expenditures;
- 34 development programs and 98 indicators were approved.

- An international seminar was organized in which experts from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the European Union, the US Treasury Department, the World Bank, ADBs shared their experiences (about 150 listeners participated). Cooperation with the European Union, US Treasury Department, World Bank, ADB and a number of international organizations was established.

In 2022-2023:

- Target indicators of 40 ministries and agencies were developed, in which the ministries and agencies

31.7 trillion soums of budget or state budget expenditures

15.2 percent were covered by 561 indicators;

- the procedure for developing, monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of budget programs of ministries and agencies was developed;

- the practice of hearing the reports of the heads of each ministry and office on the implementation of target indicators in the chambers of the Oliy Majlis was introduced;

- acceptance of reports on the implementation of target indicators was automated through the UzASBO program;

- On the Openbudget.uz site, the implementation of target indicators has been published for the public.

In 2024:

- 574 target indicators of 31.7 trillion som budget expenditures of 37 ministries and agencies were approved;

- Norms for the formation and submission of reports on the performance of target indicators by ministries and agencies were established.

Table 1 shows an example of the formation of target indicators of the program budgeting system.

Table 1

As a result of the implementation of the software budgeting system, the following advantages are achieved.

It will be possible to determine the amount of funds directed to the priorities of the national strategy and the goals of sustainable development;
effective use of resources allocated to priority goals is ensured;
public and parliamentary control over targeted and effective spending of budget and other resources is established;

Open use of the state budget, extrabudgetary funds and grant funds is ensured;

Increases the effectiveness and efficiency of budget expenditures, and creates a mechanism for evaluating their effectiveness.

References:

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